

The free, open repository from OpenAIRE and CERN

FACTSHEET FOR RESEARCHERS, SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITIES AND RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS

What is ZENODO?

Zenodo (zenodo.org) is an open, dependable repository for all of scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format.

Free to upload and free to access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term.

What is ZENODO for?

- a.** Zenodo is for all individual researchers, scientific communities and research institutions. It is open to all research outputs regardless of funding source.
- b.** Don't have an appropriate institutional or thematic repository? Use Zenodo!
- c.** Zenodo is linked to Horizon 2020 projects and all results are immediately linked to OpenAIRE and the EC portal.
- d.** With Zenodo you can create and curate a collection for your research group or project, host conference proceedings and even small non-for-profit journals.

What can do for you?

Share and link research: Zenodo provides a rich interface which enables linking research outputs to datasets and funding information. All open content is harvestable via OAI-PMH by third parties.

Supports versioning: Via a top-level DOI you can support all the different versions of a file.

Trusted, reliable, safe: Data is stored at CERN, which has considerable knowledge and experience operating large-scale digital repositories. Data files and metadata are kept in multiple online and offline copies.

Reviewing: Research materials can be set to share with reviewers only, and also as embargoed.

Share and preserve your publications, data and software for free in OpenAIRE's trusted repository hosted by CERN

Publish your research artifacts...

Make it citable...

Do it easily!

zenodo.org

How do I use Zenodo?

Share your research output in 3 steps!

Zenodo offers simple and easy-to-use data archiving with maximum autonomy.

The clear web interface allows you to easily upload your content in just a few steps.

Upload

Any size/format
Any science
Any research output

Sign-in locally or by using your
GitHub or ORCID credentials.
Easily upload files of up to 50 GB.

Describe

Reusable for others
Link to related research
Open, embargoed and closed content

Next, describe your content so others
can find it. Add funding and license
information and pre-reserve a DOI
for your upload. Optionally, you can
select a community..

Publish

Instantly available
DOI: Citeable. Discoverable.
Usage Statistics

Submit to finalize your upload and
publish. After a quick spam-check, your
content will be available immediately.
Open access uploads will also be visible
on Zenodo's front-page.

Zenodo enables and encourages you to share your research as openly as possible to maximise use and re-use of your research results. However, we also acknowledge that one size does not fit all. Therefore, while we encourage open licenses where possible, we also allow for uploading under a variety of different licenses and access levels.

Short Facts about Zenodo

- ★ Catch-all repository for EU funded research
- ★ Up to 50 GB per upload
- ★ Data stored in the CERN Data Center
- ★ Persistent identifiers (DOIs) for every upload
- ★ Usage Statistics
- ★ Free for the long tail of science
- ★ Open to all research outputs from all disciplines
- ★ Github integration
- ★ Easily add EC funding information and report via OpenAIRE

About OpenAIRE

www.openaire.eu

Shifting scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research.

For more information, please contact: info@openaire.eu

Additional Guidance: www.openaire.eu/guides

Useful Links

Zenodo Homepage: www.zenodo.org

More about Zenodo: <https://about.zenodo.org/>

CERN: <https://home.cern/>